

Retrofit Strategies

**Energy aware BIM Cloud Platform in a
Cost-effective Building Renovation Context
- ENCORE -**

2022

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

www.encorebim.eu

@encorebim

Retrofit Strategies

This report presents the results that have been performed based on the analysis of case studies in order to propose possible retrofitting strategies that can be used to reduce the energy consumption.

Retrofitting measures have been identified and described in the following sections, classified by Building Typologies, Climates Zones and Types of Retrofit Strategies. Recommendations are proposed for Southern Europe, Central Europe and Northern Europe.

The methodology proposed uses three European climate zones (Figure 1) with five typologies of residential buildings (Figure 2).

European climate regions

European countries have been divided based upon climatic similarities into three regions (Figure 1): North, Central and South. Three European cities located in different climatic zones have been selected: Madrid (South), Berlin (Central) and Helsinki (North).

Figure 1. European climate regions: North, Central and South.

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building Typologies

Residential buildings in large European cities have been categorised regarding the generic qualities and similarities, in five typologies according to the shape of the layout (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Typology of buildings: 3D views (above) for building in (a) Rectangle Shape; (b) Tower Shape; (c) L Shape; (d) C Shape (e) With Inner Courtyard.

Figure 2 shows the five building models, as well as the number of dwellings per floor and the number of levels, which are described in the following paragraph:

1. The building in Rectangle Shape design (Figure 2a) has 8 dwellings: 2 dwellings per floor, 4 levels in total.
2. The building in Tower Shape design (Figure 2b) has 44 dwellings: 4 dwellings per floor, 11 levels in total.
3. The building in L Shape design (Figure 2c) has 55 dwellings: 3 dwellings per floor with 4 communication cores (one of the communication cores only has two dwellings per floor), 5 levels in total.
4. The building in C Shape design (Figure 2d) has 84 dwellings: 2 dwellings per floor with 7 communication cores, 6 floor levels in total.
5. The building with an Inner Courtyard (Figure 2e) has 72 dwellings: 2 dwellings per floor with six communication cores, 6 floor levels in total.

Types of Retrofit Strategies

On the basis of experience of technical experts from different countries and the analysis carried out of case studies, a database on types of retrofit strategies has been created, which are described in the following paragraph:

1. **Building Envelope.** Thermal retrofitting of building envelope is one of the most frequently applied retrofitting measures. It considers the different building elements: (a) insulation systems, (b) windows, (c) insulation systems + windows replacing and (d) over-cladding systems.
2. **Heating Systems.** The modernization of the heating systems can be a crucial action for the final result of energy conservation related to retrofitting of residential buildings. It refers especially to the well-insulated buildings with relatively low heat demand.
3. **Cooling Systems and Solar Control.** The overview of retrofitting scenarios referring to solar control and cooling techniques, including shading systems, cooling systems and air conditioning systems.

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Retrofit Strategies

Recommendations Northern Europe

Zero or low-cost investment

Without economic investment, the energy consumption of buildings can be controlled through the correct adjustment of temperatures in the thermostats as well as with the correct maintenance and use of heating equipment. During the winter months, the capture of as much solar radiation as possible through the windows should be encouraged.

Domestic hot water consumes between 20-30% of the overall energy consumption. To reduce domestic hot water consumption, it is important to have a shower instead of a bath, daily shower time under 5 minutes, close the shower tap when soaping yourself, close the tap when brushing your teeth, close the tap when shaving and leave tap on cold water position after use.

The lighting consumption of an average house implies about 10-20% of the total electricity invoice. Using low-consumption or LED-type lighting, as well as favoring the use of natural light as far as possible, will contribute to reducing energy consumption for lighting.

Medium or large cost investment

Insulation thickness between 160 and 240 mm achieves optimum energy savings, taking into account the cost values of installation of insulation and energy savings.

The improvement of the window frames as well as the use of double glazing will improve the behavior of the building in relation to heating consumption. The transmittance value of the assembly must be around 1.5 W/m²K.

From the point of view of active systems for controlling the interior temperature of spaces, the use of highly energy-efficient heating and cooling equipment and their control units will also help reduce energy consumption in buildings.

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Retrofit Strategies

01 Insulation

Building Envelope

Insulation strategies need to be suited to the property in question and the performance requirements being sought. External wall insulation can impact on poorly constructed extensions, eliminating some thermal bridges. The solution consists in locating new insulation layers on the facade to the lack or poor quality of the existing insulation.

We could improve the building envelope locating insulation layers on the external façades. We could achieve consumption energy savings between 28-49% in heating consumption and 10-37% in cooling consumption. The percentage of improvement depends on building typology, climate zone and thickness of the insulation layer: 40 mm, 80 mm, 120 mm or 160 mm (see in figures and tables below). The insulation thickness = 0 mm corresponds to the simulation of a building with an air gap of 50 mm.

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Rectangle Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm achieves optimum energy savings, taking into account the cost values of installation of insulation and energy savings.
For residential buildings, adopting 120 mm or 160 mm of insulation thickness does not present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² ·year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	188.86	-
40 mm	123.99	34.35
80 mm	106.38	43.67
120 mm	98.78	47.70
160 mm	94.56	49.93

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² ·year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.27	-
40 mm	0.17	37.04
80 mm	0.17	37.04
120 mm	0.18	33.33
160 mm	0.18	33.33

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Tower Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm achieves optimum energy savings, taking into account the cost values of installation of insulation and energy savings.

For residential buildings, adopting 120 mm or 160 mm of insulation thickness does not present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building in Tower Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building in Tower Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	199.94	-
40 mm	138.87	30.54
80 mm	121.04	39.46
120 mm	113.52	43.22
160 mm	109.07	45.45

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.34	-
40 mm	0.29	14.71
80 mm	0.29	14.71
120 mm	0.30	11.76
160 mm	0.30	11.76

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
L Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:
Insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm achieves optimum energy savings, taking into account the cost values of installation of insulation and energy savings.
For residential buildings, adopting 120 mm or 160 mm of insulation thickness does not present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building in L Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building in LShape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² ·year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	169.56	-
40 mm	118.72	29.98
80 mm	104.94	38.11
120 mm	98.84	41.71
160 mm	95.48	43.69

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² ·year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.39	-
40 mm	0.33	15.38
80 mm	0.34	12.82
120 mm	0.34	12.82
160 mm	0.35	10.26

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
C Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm achieves optimum energy savings, taking into account the cost values of installation of insulation and energy savings.
For residential buildings, adopting 120 mm or 160 mm of insulation thickness does not present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building in C Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building in C Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	152.96	-
40 mm	108.72	28.92
80 mm	96.66	36.81
120 mm	91.34	40.29
160 mm	88.41	42.20

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.26	-
40 mm	0.22	15.38
80 mm	0.22	15.38
120 mm	0.22	15.38
160 mm	0.23	11.54

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Building with Inner Courtyard

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:
 Insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm achieves optimum energy savings, taking into account the cost values of installation of insulation and energy savings.
 For residential buildings, adopting 120 mm or 160 mm of insulation thickness does not present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building with Inner Courtyard & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption by Insulation Thickness

Building with Inner Courtyard & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	150.49	-
40 mm	107.08	28.85
80 mm	95.29	36.68
120 mm	90.08	40.14
160 mm	87.22	42.04

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.23	-
40 mm	0.18	21.74
80 mm	0.19	17.39
120 mm	0.19	17.39
160 mm	0.19	17.39

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Retrofit Strategies

02 Replacing Windows

Building Envelope

Insulation strategies need to be suited to the property in question and the performance requirements being sought. Windows are still the least insulating part of the thermal envelope with a heat loss coefficient, a U-value, which is typically 4-10 times higher than that of other thermal envelope elements. The proposed solution consists in replacing the existing windows by others with double glazing and PVC frame. The window type has a single-chamber insulated glazing unit: 4mm thick outer pane / 16mm wide spacer / 6mm thick inner pane. Inter-pane space filled with air (see figure below).

The analysis carried out shows that we could achieve consumption energy savings between 8-20% in heating consumption and 5-17% in cooling consumption. The percentage of improvement depends on building typology, climate zone and thickness of the insulation layer: 40 mm, 80 mm, 120 mm or 160 mm (see in figures and tables below). The building consumption was compared to that of a building with windows with simple glazing unit 6mm thick for the same layer of insulation.

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Rectangle Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 8% to 18% in heating consumption.

For residential buildings with only an air gap (0 mm), replacing windows reaches consumption energy savings around 8% in heating and 11% in cooling consumption.

Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness between 40 mm and 80 mm present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)"

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² ·year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	173.20	8.29
40 mm	107.38	13.40
80 mm	89.34	16.02
120 mm	81.50	17.49
160 mm	77.08	18.49

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² ·year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.24	11.11
40 mm	0.14	17.65
80 mm	0.14	17.65
120 mm	0.15	16.67
160 mm	0.16	11.11

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Tower Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 8% to 17% in heating consumption. For residential buildings with only an air gap (0 mm), replacing windows reaches consumption energy savings around 8% in heating and 11% in cooling consumption. Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness 40 mm present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	182.66	8.64
40 mm	120.56	13.18
80 mm	102.19	15.57
120 mm	94.33	16.90
160 mm	89.87	17.60

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.30	11.76
40 mm	0.24	17.24
80 mm	0.25	13.79
120 mm	0.26	13.33
160 mm	0.26	13.33

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
L Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 10% to 19% in heating consumption.
For residential buildings with only an air gap (0 mm), replacing windows reaches consumption energy savings around 10% in heating and 10% in cooling consumption.
Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness 40 mm present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

Building in L Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

Building in L Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	152.05	10.33
40 mm	100.45	15.39
80 mm	86.42	17.65
120 mm	80.26	18.80
160 mm	76.82	19.54

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.35	10.26
40 mm	0.30	9.09
80 mm	0.31	8.82
120 mm	0.31	8.82
160 mm	0.33	5.71

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
C Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 10% to 19% in heating consumption. For residential buildings with only an air gap (0 mm), replacing windows reaches consumption energy savings around 10% in heating and 11% in cooling consumption. Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness 40 mm present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

Building in C Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

Building in C Shape & Climate in North European Region - Helsinki

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	136.84	10.54
40 mm	91.94	15.43
80 mm	76.61	20.74
120 mm	74.23	18.73
160 mm	71.22	19.44

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.23	11.54
40 mm	0.19	13.64
80 mm	0.20	9.09
120 mm	0.20	9.09
160 mm	0.21	8.70

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Building with Inner Courtyard

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:
 Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 10% to 19% in heating consumption.
 For residential buildings with only an air gap (0 mm), replacing windows reaches consumption energy savings around 10% in heating and 13% in cooling consumption.
 Replacing windows for buildings with insulation thickness between 40 mm and 80 mm present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption replacing Windows (Glazing + Frame)

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	134.84	10.40
40 mm	90.81	15.19
80 mm	78.76	17.35
120 mm	73.50	18.41
160 mm	70.56	19.10

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.20	13.04
40 mm	0.16	11.11
80 mm	0.16	15.79
120 mm	0.16	15.79
160 mm	0.17	10.53

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Retrofit Strategies

03 Insulation + Replacing Windows Building Envelope

The proposed solution consists in combination the above strategies: locating new insulation layers on the facades and replacing the existing windows. The window type has a single-chamber insulated glazing unit: 4mm thick outer pane / 16mm wide spacer / 6mm thick inner pane. Inter-pane space filled with air (see figure below).

We could achieve consumption energy savings between 32-55% in heating consumption and 5-41% in cooling consumption. The percentage of improvement depends on building typology, climate zone and thickness of the insulation layer: 40 mm, 80 mm, 120 mm or 160 mm (see in figures and tables below).

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Rectangle Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings in addition to insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 38% to 55% in heating consumption and from 41% to 33% in cooling consumption.

Locating new insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm in addition to replacing windows present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	173.20	-
40 mm	107.38	38.00
80 mm	89.34	48.42
120 mm	81.50	52.94
160 mm	77.08	55.50

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.24	-
40 mm	0.14	41.67
80 mm	0.14	41.67
120 mm	0.15	37.50
160 mm	0.16	33.33

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Tower Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings in addition to insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 34% to 50% in heating consumption and from 13% to 20% in cooling consumption.

Locating new insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm in addition to replacing windows present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	182.66	-
40 mm	120.56	34.00
80 mm	102.19	44.05
120 mm	94.33	48.36
160 mm	89.87	50.80

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.30	-
40 mm	0.24	20.00
80 mm	0.25	16.67
120 mm	0.26	13.33
160 mm	0.26	13.33

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
L Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings in addition to insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 33% to 49% in heating consumption and from 5% to 14% in cooling consumption. Locating new insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm in addition to replacing windows present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

■ % Energy Savings in Heating Consumption adding Insulation and...

■ % Energy Savings in Cooling Consumption adding Insulation and Replacing Windows

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	152.05	-
40 mm	100.45	33.94
80 mm	86.42	43.16
120 mm	80.26	47.21
160 mm	76.82	49.48

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.35	-
40 mm	0.30	14.29
80 mm	0.31	11.43
120 mm	0.31	11.43
160 mm	0.33	5.71

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
C Shape

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings in addition to insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 32% to 47% in heating consumption and from 8% to 17% in cooling consumption. Locating new insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm in addition to replacing windows present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	136.84	-
40 mm	91.94	32.81
80 mm	76.61	44.01
120 mm	74.23	45.75
160 mm	71.22	47.95

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.23	-
40 mm	0.19	17.39
80 mm	0.20	13.04
120 mm	0.20	13.04
160 mm	0.21	8.70

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

Building typology:
Building with Inner Courtyard

Climate Zone:
North European Region - Helsinki

Recommendations:

Replacing windows for buildings in addition to insulation thickness between 0 and 160 mm achieves percentage of energy savings from 32% to 47% in heating consumption and from 15% to 20% in cooling consumption. Locating new insulation thickness between 40 and 80 mm in addition to replacing windows present an optimal choice in terms of price/performance ratio.

Insulation Thickness	Heating Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Heating Energy Savings
0 mm	134.84	-
40 mm	90.81	32.65
80 mm	78.76	41.59
120 mm	73.50	45.49
160 mm	70.56	47.67

Insulation Thickness	Cooling Consumption (kWh/m ² -year)	% Cooling Energy Savings
0 mm	0.20	-
40 mm	0.16	20.00
80 mm	0.16	20.00
120 mm	0.16	20.00
160 mm	0.17	15.00

The ENCORE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820434

